

Citation

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A job satisfaction index to investigate the relationship between employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment

Abstract

Employees are different from each other, and their expectations also differ. Hence, it is a challenge to identify different expectations of employees to make employees more satisfied and committed, and hence minimize turnover intention and job search behaviour of employees. This study was carried out to identify the predictors of job satisfaction and its relationship with employee commitment, Turnover intention, and job search behaviour. The design of the survey was quantitative using a structured questionnaire. The target group was managerial-level employees in the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka. The questionnaire included relevant measures of all variables that were tested in previous studies. The results of factor analysis, correlation, and regression were used to identify the predictors of job satisfaction, and further, it was found that job satisfaction and employee commitment are positively related, and job satisfaction and turnover intention are negatively related, but there is a mediatory relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour. The main implication of this survey is the inability to generalize the findings to other companies in Sri Lanka due to the different attitudes of employees in different sectors. Hence, there is a future research opportunity to conduct the same survey among a very robust sample, including employees from different industries, enabling the generation of findings for employees in other industries in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Employee Commitment, Turnover Intention, Job Search Behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Organizational scholars have long been interested in why people's level of job satisfaction (JS) tends to differ from each other (Locke, 1976). This drives a need to understand and explain factors that drive JS and the consequences of JS. According to Meyer (1999), the employees who do not have JS in their work are low in commitment to their work. In turn, it impacts their performance and the achievement of organizational goals. The symptoms of these problems are low productivity, high absenteeism, labour unrest, industrial action, and high labour turnover. According to the studies that have been conducted by Barnett (1995), it was found that turnover is a major problem for companies in many Asian countries, such as South Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, and Taiwan (Khatri et al., 2001). The main controllable factors of employee turnover are JS and employee commitment (EC). When it comes to JS, it can be the satisfaction with pay, nature of work, supervision, and so on. Hence, it is important for organizations to identify areas of employee dissatisfaction and take action to rectify those. According to Armstrong (2004), the level of JS is affected by intrinsic and extrinsic motivating factors, the quality of supervision, social relationships between work groups, and the degree to

which individuals succeed or fail in their work. Purcet et al. (2003) believe that discretionary behaviour that helps the firm to be successful is most likely to happen when employees are well motivated and feel committed to the organization, and when the job gives them the highest level of JS. Now, employee attitude measurement studies have become more important and are periodically practiced in most organizations in the world since the importance of feelings and attitudes, besides the competencies and experiences, in the effectiveness of employees has been realized. Among those studies, JS studies have been the most examined type of attitude surveys since JS plays a crucial role in the overall subjective well-being of employees, and at the same time, the subjective well-being can be considered as “the central economic variable driving individuals’ decisions”. According to Mallilo (1990), JS was dependent on a number of different factors and was subject to change. Administrators should conduct periodic needs assessments to determine the level of JS of personnel and identify methods for increasing satisfaction. Hence, researching the causes and consequences of JS has also become a periodic exercise done by many HR managers and CEOs of many companies in Asian countries, too.

Hence, we identified the importance of studying JS and evaluating its relationship with some main consequences, such as EC, job search behaviour (JSB), and turnover intention (TI). Telecommunication sector companies were selected for the purpose of this survey. The concept of JS is a frequently studied area in work and organizational literature, and this concept has been investigated by several disciplines such as psychology, sociology, economics, and management sciences as well. This has happened mainly due to the fact that many experts believe that JS trends can affect employees’ behaviour and influence work productivity, work effort, employee absenteeism, staff turnover, employee motivation, and employee retention. Moreover, JS is considered a strong predictor of overall individual well-being as well as a good predictor of intentions or decisions of employees to leave a job. Workers’ decisions about whether to work or not, what kind of job to accept or stay in, and how hard to work are all likely to depend in part upon the worker’s subjective evaluation of their work, in other words, on their JS (Clark, 2001; Jinadasa and Wickramasinghe, 2005). Work experiences have profound effects on both the individual employee and society as a whole. Furthermore, “research evidence clearly shows that employees’ decisions about whether they will go to work on any given day and whether they will quit are affected by their feelings of JS” (Jaime, 2004). Enhancing employees’ JS will help in creating committed and loyal employees in organizations, and hence it will start saving on employee turnover costs. Hence, the trend to measure the JS has become a human resource practice in many organizations in Sri Lanka as well. But no such studies have been carried out to build up a job satisfaction index to refer to for any sector in Sri Lanka, and also to identify the consequences of JS. Hence, the purpose of this research study was to build a Job Satisfaction Index and identify the factors that affect JS and its impact on EC, TI, and JSB.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the level of job satisfaction of managerial-level employees in the telecommunication sector and evaluate the organizational factors that affect the job satisfaction of employees.
2. To measure the impact of job satisfaction on employee commitment.
3. To measure the impact of job satisfaction on the turnover intention of employees.
4. To measure the impact of job satisfaction on the job search behaviour of employees.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Job satisfaction and organizational factors affect job satisfaction

After reading all the possible satisfaction theories, it is clear that employees are looking for many things from their organization in return for the work they do. Different people have different requirements that need to be fulfilled. Hence, it is a responsibility of the organization's administration or human resource management to understand the different needs of employees and formulate strategies that would satisfy them. Therefore, it is noteworthy to understand the factors or variables that are expected by the majority of employees in organizations, which really determine their satisfaction. Whereby, the management of organizations will be able to utilize their resources profitably to fulfil those factors that drive employee satisfaction. According to Scott (2004), administrators need to know and understand what their employees want from the organization to ensure a high level of JS and to minimize job dissatisfaction. Herzberg et al. (1959) argued that one of the major reasons for measuring JS is to answer the question, "What does the worker want from his/her job?" and that the answer to this question will assist management in discovering new methods of motivating employees (Long and Swartzel, 2007).

Most of traditional JS research has concluded that employees are generally looking for stable employment, a promotional path within the organization, and most importantly, satisfactory compensation (DeSantis and Durst, 1996). Several studies on employees explained factors like flexible working hours, social satisfaction, and the characteristics and behaviour of superiors as variables that affect employee JS (Akuratiyagamage, 2003; Amarakoon and Wickramasinghe, 2010; Daley, 1986; Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe, 2007; Kumara and Wickramasinghe, 2006; Wanniarachchi and Wickramasinghe, 2010). Conclusions of such research present that the JS is a multivariate concept, which is a product of many other different variables operating on employees. Salary, benefits, job security, and the ability to retire within the organization are some of the reasons for retaining within the organization. Impact of management actions on employee JS has also been discovered (Amarakoon and Wickramasinghe, 2010; Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe, 2006; Long and Swartzel, 2007; Mamman and Akuratiyagamage, 2005; Wanniarachchi et al., 2008). According to Whitt (2004), management actions impact JS positively as well as negatively based on the nature of the management actions. Mallilo (1990) emphasised the importance of assessing JS periodically as it is affected by several organizational as well as demographic factors. Further, Mallilo (1990) highlighted the importance of identifying factors that are influencing JS, where the organizations can work on those particular areas to maintain and improve JS (Long and Swartzel, 2007). Performance evaluation is one of the main HR practices in most of the companies nowadays. Continuous, accurate, and objective staff evaluation was essential in improving JS, performance and productivity. According to Long and Swartzel (2007), performance evaluation should be done on standards that employees perceive to be fair, important, achievable, and equal for all. Further, Long and Swartzel (2007) noted that individual characteristics were not as important for motivation as were JS factors. Consequently, organizational administrations could improve employee morale and JS by paying less attention to personal characteristics of employees and focusing more on factors in JS such as evaluation, dependable supervisors, work incentives, pay, praise, and job security (Long and Swartzel, 2007). Salary, type of job, physical conditions, relations with colleagues, security, promotion opportunities, empowerment, status, financial and morale awards, training, being involved in decision making, communication, social activities, policy, and management of organizations are some of the driving factors of JS. As a general tendency, people leave

establishments because of dissatisfaction with salary, mobbing from peers or superiors, or disagreement with human resources management policies (Aksu and Aktas, 2005). As per the surveys done by Herzberg et al. (1959), two fundamental variables are crucially important in attaining JS among workers. Among those variables, the job's internal rewards, such as challenging work, and external rewards, such as fair compensation and fringe benefits, are the ones that drive JS (Kumara and Wickramasinghe, 2006). With reference to an organizational context, there are several factors that lead to JS and dissatisfaction. On an overall level, these include hygienic factors, motivational factors, hidden factors, and potential factors.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between organizational factors and job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction and its consequences

Numerous studies have highlighted that JS impacts EC, TI, and JSB (Mowday et al. 1982, Akerlof et al., 1988; Clark, 2001). Employee's JS is an attitude that people have about their jobs and the organizations in which they perform these jobs. Methodologically, we can define JS as an employee's affective reaction to a job, based on a comparison between actual outcomes and desired outcomes (Rad and Yarmohammadian, 2006). Justifying the importance of investigating JS is exemplified in the seemingly observed relationship between the levels of job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, grievance expression, tardiness, low morale, and high turnover (Akuratiyagamage, 2003). JS is an immediate antecedent of the intention to leave the workplace and labour turnover (Rad and Yarmohammadian, 2006). Unsatisfied workers will leave their jobs more than their satisfied colleagues (Rad and Yarmohammadian, 2006). Retention and turnover of staff, particularly highly skilled personnel, are important issues for managers in organizations. Employees who experience JS are more likely to be productive and stay on the job (Rad and Yarmohammadian, 2006). The probability that a worker willingly leaves his job decreases with JS, even after controlling for several worker and job characteristics. The strength of this negative relation between JS and turnover has been recognized in Akerlof et al. (1988) and Clark (2001). Further, Clark (2001) showed that not only overall JS, but also satisfaction with several job domains, correlates with the probability that a worker quits (Delfgaauw, 2006).

Some other research concludes that the negative effect of JS on employee mobility runs through turnover intentions or job search behaviour of employees. (Delfgaauw, 2006). Sousa-Poza (2000) explored a strongly negative relation between JS and intentions to quit in a cross-national analysis covering countries, similar to what Shields and Price (2002) found in a sample of British nurses. Further evidence of the strong link between JS and both intentions to quit and job search was provided in a survey (Delfgaauw, 2006). The link between TI or job search and actual turnover has been established (Delfgaauw, 2006). While there is extensive literature on JS and EC in organizational settings, the persistence of motivation is sustained by commitment. Commitment is a course of action that is of relevance to a particular target. It will encourage discretionary behaviour that will result in positive goal outcomes and hence reinforce EC to the organization. Although these two concepts are related, the literature was developed independently. According to Rensburg (2004), intrinsic JS and extrinsic JS are causes of EC. Job satisfaction and EC are interrelated, as more satisfied employees are, the more committed they are. (Silva, 2006). As mentioned above, organizational commitment and JS are significantly related to one another, with the basic proposition that JS is an antecedent of organizational commitment since it takes longer to form, and this too happens only after one is satisfied with their job (Mowday et. al., 1982). While organizational commitment becomes a positively correlated consequence of JS, many studies report a consistent and negative relationship between JS and TI and JSB (Price, 1977), as dissatisfied employees are more likely

to leave an organization than satisfied ones. An essential element in any retention strategy is to ensure that employees remain committed to their organization. Job satisfaction has been recognized as a component of EC by Kovach in 1987. JS is a significant predictor of organizational commitment. Further, this has been supported by Porter et al. (1974), Price (1977), and Rose (2003). According to Mowday et al. (1982), the difference between EC and JS is seen in several ways. Commitment is a more global response to an organization, whereas JS is more of a response to a specific job or various facets of the job. Job satisfaction is so important in that its absence often leads to lethargy and reduced employee commitment.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee commitment

Hypothesis 3: There is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and employees' turnover intention and job search behaviour

The relevant schematic diagram is shown in Figure 1. Job satisfaction is labeled as the independent variable. Employee commitment, turnover intention, and job search behaviour are labeled as dependent variables.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the research framework

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The quantitative research technique has been used for this survey, as the objective was to assess the relationship between variables. The main purpose of this study was to establish the type of relationship between dependent and independent variables of the survey framework. Therefore, the purpose of the study was explanatory or hypothesis testing. It is within the interest of the present study to explain the influence of organizational factors on JS and the influence of JS on its consequences, rather than establishing a definite cause-and-effect relationship. Hence, the type of investigation of this survey was correlational. None of the variables were manipulated or controlled. As the study was conducted in the natural environment where events normally occur, that is, a non-contrived setting. No artificial or contrived settings were created for the study. This study took two months for the collection of data. The data for the study were collected within a particular time period, and there were no later extensions of the research

contemplated. The unit of the study was at the group level: managerial-level employees in the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka.

Operationalization of variables

The variables in this research model are antecedents of JS, JS, and its consequences, which were measured through a questionnaire with five-point scales, which were completed by the respondents (employees) themselves, based on their experience. The variables of the study constitute interval scales.

Job Satisfaction: The JS of managerial-level employees in the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka was measured as one item global measure of JS. According to Gyekye and Salminen (2006), the single-item measure of overall JS is considered to be more robust than scale measures. And also, this measurement has been used extensively in the organizational behaviour literature (Gyekye and Salminen, 2006). A five-point Likert scale was used to measure JS, where response categories ranged from “extremely satisfied” to “not at all satisfied”, corresponding to the 5-point response format. (1=Not at all satisfied to 5=extremely satisfied). Higher scores in this scale reflect higher satisfaction, lower scores lower level satisfaction, and a score of 3 indicates neutral responses.

Antecedents of JS: The interest was to identify the critical factors that drive JS of employees in an organization. Organizational factors which also have significant similarities with determinant of JS dealt with in previous research (Jenning,1998; Whitt, 2004; Mwangi, 1994; Testa M.R., 1999; Lok and Crawford, 2001; Bartolo and Furlonger, 2000; Savery L.K, 1991; Choo S. and Bowley, 2007; Seymour and Busherhof, 1991; Carr and Kazanowski, 1994; DeSantis and Durst, 1996; Daley, 1986; Aksu and Aktas, 2005) were used in this study. Table 1 shows the organizational factors of JS used in this study. Each dimension was measured using relevant attributes, which were tested for validity before the survey. Each attribute was measured using five-point Likert scales to measure the level of satisfaction (1=Not at all satisfied to 5=extremely satisfied) in order to evaluate the sub-dimensions of overall satisfaction.

Table 1. Organization factors of JS

Code	Organization factors
1	Vision/mission (targets) of the company
2	Leadership of top management
3	Capability of top management
4	Supervision and leadership of immediate supervisors
5	Organizational culture
6	Type of work
7	Payments & compensation
8	Working environment
9	Grievance procedure
10	Internal communication & working relationship
11	Performance evaluation
12	Training & development
13	Changing process
14	External image of the organization
15	Internal image of the organization

Consequences of JS: Most of the surveys have been carried out in the area of JS and its consequences. Among many consequences of JS, EC, TI, and JSB are the most researched areas in the literature. These consequences of JS were measured using the following variables in a five-point Likert scale in the questionnaire.

Table 2. Consequences of JS and their attributes

Variables	Attributes	Indicators	Source
Employee commitment	01. Identification with the goals and values of the organization	Five-point Likert Scale 1= Strongly disagree 5= Strongly agree	Allen and Meyer (1990)
	02. A desire to belong to the organization		
	03. A willingness to display effort on behalf of the organization		
Job search behaviour	Time spent on job search behaviour activities	Five-point Likert Scale No time at all = 1 Very much time =5	Van Hooft et al. (2004)
Turnover intention	01. Intention to quit the organization	Five-point Likert Scale Almost never=1 Almost everyday=5	Meyer et al. (2004)
	02. Likelihood of quitting the organization	Five-point Likert Scale Very likely=1 Very unlikely=5	

Method of data collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. A questionnaire was prepared in a way that the employees could simply click on the correct answer on the scale provided with check boxes. The questionnaire had six sections. Part one was to assess overall JS. The second part consisted of questions to elicit the EC and the nature of the commitment of employees. Part three of the questionnaire was to evaluate the JSB of employees. Part four of the questionnaire consisted of two questions to measure the level of TI from the organization. The fifth part of the questionnaire focused on factors that drive JS. 15 dimensions that were included as factors that influence JS. The final/ sixth section of the questionnaire consisted of demographic information about individuals. All sections of the questionnaire were arranged to collect maximum possible information to analyze all research objectives, minimize missing values, and enhance confidentiality. As the collecting of demographic information was not a primary objective of the survey, it was included at the end of the questionnaire, which helped to eliminate of efforts could be taken to hide information in the other areas of the questionnaire.

Procedure: questionnaires were pretested at pilot interviews, which were conducted with a convenience sample of three managerial-level employees selected from three different companies in the sample. Each of these respondents completed the preliminary version of the questionnaire and provided feedback about the administration time, clarity of the questions, and directions provided to fill in the questionnaire. In general, respondents indicated that the questionnaire was relatively clear and easy to complete, as it involved simply clicking on the relevant answer, and due to the clear instructions provided on how to fill in the questionnaire. But the length of the questionnaire was a concern. Following the pilot test, the questionnaire was modified further to improve the quality of measures. The questionnaire also included a cover letter indicating the purpose and importance of the study, and caution was taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity in data collection to reduce self-report bias. The modified questionnaire was distributed to the selected sample of 150 employees. Caution was taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity in data collection to reduce self-report bias. One week after the initial emailing of questionnaires, follow-up emails were sent to all employees. This

letter emphasized the importance of employees' responses, and contact details were provided to call for any clarification required in the questionnaire. Accordingly, a total of 53 questionnaires were returned within 8 weeks. The response rate for the survey is 35 percent.

Sample of the study

The participants of this study were managerial-level employees working for the telecommunications sector organizations. Mainly, there are seven telecommunication companies in this sector at present, which represent three types of organizations. Those are: organizations which are backed by private and public properties (semi-government), fully private fixed line/CDMA service providers, and GSM/mobile service providers. Although the interest was to cover all seven companies in this industry, management approvals were given only by three organizations. However, leading telecommunication companies in Sri Lanka were represented in this survey. 53 permanent managerial-level employees participated in this survey. Respondents were selected using a simple random sampling technique. A demographic characteristic of the sample is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

<u>Gender</u>		<u>Total number of years in service (any place)</u>	
Male	71.2%	1-3 years	11.5%
Female	28.8%	4-6 years	25%
<u>Marital Status</u>		7-9 years	21.2%
Single	30.8%	9-11 years	3.8%
Married	67.3%	11 years and over	36.5%
Not mentioned	1.9%	Not mentioned	1.9%
<u>Age</u>		<u>Total number of years in service within the current company</u>	
21-25 years old	9.6%	Less than 1 year	3.8%
26-30 years old	36.5%	1-3 years	36.5%
31-35 years old	21.2%	4-6 years	19.2%
36-40 years old	13.5%	7-9 years	15.4%
41-45 years old	11.5%	9-11 years	9.6%
45-50 years old	3.8%	11 years and over	11.5%
Older than 50 years	1.9%	Not mentioned	3.8%
Not mentioned	1.9%		
<u>Level of Education</u>		<u>Year of service in the current position</u>	
Up to (O/L)	1.9%	Less than 1 year	19.2%
Up to (A/L)	11.5%	1-3 years	55.8%
Up to basic degree/ diploma level	38.5%	4-6 years	9.6%
Postgraduate	44.2%	7-9 years	1.9%
Not mentioned	3.8%	9-11 years	5.8%
		11 years and over	5.8%
		Not mentioned	1.9%
<u>Department of working</u>			
Marketing Sales & Customer Service		42.3%	
Human Resources Management		15.4%	
Accounts & Finance		9.6%	
Admin, IT, Operation & Maintenance		26.9%	
R & D		1.9%	
Not mentioned		3.8%	

Validity and reliability testing of the instrument

According to Field (2005, p 667), reliability means that a scale should consistently reflect the construct it is measuring. The reliability reported in Cronbach's alpha of each scale is presented in Table 4 with the number of items used to measure each scale. This table presents a breakdown of each of the scales, their related Cronbach-alpha score calculated for this study. The Cronbach's alpha score of all attributes is higher than .50.

Table 4. Reliability test of variables

Scale	Number of items	alpha
Employee commitment	3	.61
Turnover Intention	2	.61

Method of data analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS). The analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Responses to items measuring different dimensions of job satisfaction, employee commitment, and turnover intention were factor-analysed, and factor scores obtained were used for successive data analysis. Multiple regression analysis was used to determine the real organizational factors that drive employees' JS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One-item global measure of JS was used to measure the overall job satisfaction (OJS) of employees in the telecommunication sector organizations in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, the level of JS is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overall satisfaction rating

More than 50% of employees in the sample were moderately satisfied, whereas nearly 1/3 rd (35%) of employees in the sample were very satisfied and only 10% employees were extremely

satisfied. Accordingly, the mean rating of OJS was 3.52, which is shown in the following table (see Table 5).

Table 5. Mean & Standard Deviation for OJS

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Overall Satisfaction	3.52	0.7	0.643	0.33

Overall satisfaction ratings were weighted by 20 in order to develop a JSI for the managerial level employees in the telecommunication sector organizations in Sri Lanka. As a result, 70.38 is the JSI on a scale from 20-100, where the minimum level of JS is 20 and the maximum level of JS is 100 (See Table 6 and Figure 3)

Table 6. Statistics

SINDEX		
N	Valid	52
	Missing	0
Mean		70.3846
Median		60.0000
Mode		60.00

Figure 3: Job satisfaction index

The first hypothesis of the study was about the impact of organizational factors on JS. Out of the fifteen factors tested in this study, all factors except 'external image of the organization' had a significant positive relationship with JS. As of the Table 7, the only organizational factor with the lowest correlation (.178) to JS was 'external image of the organization'. Correlation has been tested at 99% Confidence Interval (C.I) as well as 95% C.I. At 99% C.I., the following dimensions have significantly higher correlation to JS of the selected sample of managerial level employees in the telecommunication sector organizations in Sri Lanka. Those are: internal image of the organization, capabilities of the Top management, organizational culture, grievance procedure, working environment, payment, and compensation.

Table 7. Correlation between organizational factors and JS (a)

Organizational factors	Correlation factor
A. Vision/mission (target) of the company	.425**
B1. Leadership of Top Management	.432**
B2. Capabilities of Top Management	.564**
C. Supervision & Leadership of Immediate Supervisor	.316*
D. Organizational Culture	.559**
E. Type of Work	.451**
F. Payment & Compensation	.500**
G. Working Environment	.536**
H. Grievance Procedure	.556**
I. Internal Communication & Working Relationship	.366**
J. Performance Evaluation Process	.476**
K. Training & Development	.416**
L. Changing Process	.435**
M2. Internal Image of the Company	.588**
M1. External Image of the Company	0.178

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The second hypothesis formulated in this study was that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee commitment. This hypothesis was proved through the statistical testing that was done in this study. According to Table 8, JS and EC are positively correlated at 99% C.I.

Table 8. Correlations – JS and EC

Variables	Statistics	Overall Satisfaction	Overall commitment
Overall Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.387**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.005
Overall Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.387**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

a. Listwise N=52

The third hypothesis of the study was to examine whether there is a negative relationship between JS and employees' TI and JSB. As per Table 9, it shows that there is a direct significant negative relationship between JS and TI (-.423) (see Figure 4). But there is no significant negative relationship between JS and JSB (-.240) (see Figure 5). But, there is a strong positive relationship between TI and JSB, which is 0.569 (see Table 9). It clearly shows that there is a flow of relationship between these three variables, as shown in Figure 6. It is investigated that there is a mediatory relationship between JS and JSB.

Table 9. Correlations

Variables	Statistics	Overall Satisfaction	Intention to quite from the company	Job search behaviour
Overall Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1.000	-.423**	-.240
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.002	.087
	N	52	52	52
Intention to quite from the company	Pearson Correlation	-.423**	1.000	.569**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.	.000
	N	52	52	52
Job search behaviour	Pearson Correlation	-.240	.569**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.087	.000	.
	N	52	52	52

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 4: The relationship between JS and TI

Figure 5: The relationship between JS and JSB

Figure 6: The flow of the relationship between JS, TI, and JSB

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Objective 1: Understanding the existing level of JS through the job satisfaction index and evaluating the impact of different organizational factors on JS.

Overall JS of employees was accessed and it was at a moderate level, which was depicted as a 3.52 mean score. The developed job satisfaction index for the managerial level employees in the telecommunication sector organizations in Sri Lanka is 70.38, where the minimum level of job satisfaction index is 20, and the maximum level of job satisfaction index is 100.

Out of 15 organizational factors of JS, which were tested in this study, all organizational factors except 'external image of the company' were significantly related to overall job satisfaction. It was found that the capabilities of the top management of companies, organizational cultures, payment and compensation schemes, working environment of companies, grievance procedures, and the internal image of companies are the organizational factors that are highly correlated with overall job satisfaction of managerial-level employees of the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka. This concludes that the companies with a capable management, employee-friendly organization culture, payment and compensation system, supportive working environment, grievance procedure, and internal image of organizations help to increase job satisfaction of managerial-level employees. Based on the findings of the study, Table 10 was created to show the organizational factors and their relevant attributes.

Table 10. Organizational factors and their relevant attributes

Organizational factors	Relevant attributes
Capability of top management	Management that guides towards achieving the company's objectives
	Commitment of the management towards achieving the company's objectives
	Management's capability of driving the company forward
	Management's fairness in actions when making decisions for the company
	Management's receptivity towards new ideas of their employees
Organizational culture	Open-door culture
	Treating all at equal recognition
	Consulting employees when decisions are made
	A culture that encourages employees to point out management's shortcomings
	People-oriented culture
	Process-oriented culture
Payments & compensation	Employees are given equal opportunity for career growth
	Paid according to the work they do
	Pay scales are competitive with those of the market
Working environment	Providing a promised benefit scheme
	Provision of required resources to execute the job
	Recognition of employees' efforts by their peers & superiors
	Career prospects within the company
	Adequate empowerment is provided to carry out employees' duties
	Having a clearly defined company structure
Grievance procedure	Friendly working environment
	Having a structured system to address employees' grievances
	Fairness of the grievance system
	Immediate action to address employees' grievances
Internal image of the organization	Knowledge on employee's grievance policy
	Being a customer-oriented organization
	Being an employee-oriented organization
	Being a company that has the attraction of better employees in the market
	Being a company with high job security

Objective II: Investigate the relationship between JS and EC.

There is a significant positive relationship between JS and EC. When employees are more satisfied, they get more committed to the work that they do, and it also increases their loyalty towards the company. When an employee becomes more satisfied and more committed, it helps the company to maintain a healthy employee composition within the organization. A group of employees who are highly satisfied and highly committed always drives the company towards its objectives. Hence, the findings of the study proved that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee commitment.

Objective III: Investigating the relationship between JS, TI, and JSB.

There is a significant negative relationship between JS and TI. But the findings of the study did not investigate a strong negative relationship between JS and JSB. It was found that there is a mediatory relationship between JS and JSB.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The main implication of this survey is the inability to generalize the findings of the survey to other companies in Sri Lanka. This survey was limited to managerial-level employees. Further future studies could investigate employees in different settings and at different levels in hierarchy using a larger, robust sample to ensure generalizability. Hence, there is an opportunity to expand the scope of a similar survey in the future to draw a general conclusion for all employees in the selected sector.

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